

FINTECH AND ACCESS TO FINANCE**Nishonkulov Shohruh***Kokand university 2nd year student of economics**Kokand, Uzbekistan*

Abstract: This article surveys research on the effects of digitalization on access to finance. We focus the review on access through fintech. We review the growth of three main fintech technologies, fintech lending (incl. peer-to-peer lending), crowdfunding and initial coin offerings. We discuss existing evidence on how fintech affects access to finance for firms and investors and consider the regulatory challenges it poses. We incorporate the papers in this special issue, underlining their significant contributions to our understanding of the digitalization of finance and its effects. Finally, we discuss the challenges of research in the digital finance area and propose some new avenues for future research.

Keywords: Fintech, Digital finance, Crowdfunding, Fintech lending, Initial coin offerings, Access to finance, Regulation.

Introduction

Digitalization affects markets in different ways. Traditionally, market outcomes are affected by information asymmetry, agency problems and difficulties allocating residual control rights through contracts. These make the selection process, matching, and monitoring difficult and prevent access to finance by some firms. The digitalization of finance may provide new technologies which potentially improve access to finance for firms and afford new possibilities for investors. These technologies are challenging our traditional view of intermediation. Traditional financial intermediaries, such as banks and venture capitalists, collect funds and make reallocation

decisions. Individual account holders have no say in how banks assign their deposits to loans or other funding activities. Similarly, venture capital funds collect money from institutional investors and limited partners have no say in the selection

of startups. The digitalization of finance has created two additional sets of technologies affecting intermediation. A first type of technology based on platforms facilitates matching between firms or projects and investors. Platform-based activities, such as crowdfunding and peer to peer (P2P) lending, use technology to standardize information and provide a means to settle investments but the individual chooses the project or projects he or she wishes to finance. Platform-based fintech therefore has some common features with more traditional intermediaries such as stock markets. A second type of technology provides for total disintermediation through recourse to distributed ledger technology. In this technology, there is no centralizing authority registering transactions or organizing the market. Initial coin offerings (ICOs) are an example of full disintermediation at the issuance stage, although at the secondary listing stage they join exchanges with a matching activity.

Until now, fintech has mostly concentrated on financing start-ups and small firms. In the search for finance, entrepreneurs and firms face substantial challenges. Seed funding is scarce, translating into large funding gaps for startups and later stage. In addition, the traditional equity and debt funding channels have proven to face substantial challenges, leaving small firms with insufficient finance. On the other side of the market, potentially willing investors face serious barriers excluding them from funding early ventures. The lack of reliable information about innovative projects and the quality of firms and entrepreneurs is a central concern for unsophisticated investors. In addition, transaction costs of financing through traditional intermediaries are prohibitive and the impossibility of investing small amounts creates almost insurmountable barriers to entry to the market for a large section of potential investors. From the point of view of the regulator, furthering access to finance for early ventures and small firms creates substantial problems. How can access to finance be enhanced for firms without damaging investors? How can funding be targeted towards good projects and the funding of fraudulent projects be avoided? How can benefits beyond financial returns be captured by firms?

The growth of fintech

In this section, our focus on firms' access to finance centers our analysis on the fintech solutions regarded as the main alternative funding sources for firms and entrepreneurs, namely crowdfunding, fintech lending (including P2P lending), and ICOs. The main driver behind the initial growth of fintech is advances in technology, which reveal a relative inefficiency of traditional financing channels. Traditional financial intermediaries, such as banks, venture capitalists and stock markets, enhance investment efficiency through careful screening and the efficient distribution of returns. Their screening and monitoring advantage results from their superior capacity to gather and process information and their power to act in case of problems. Fintech firms bring novel information technologies and innovative methods to the market, opening new possibilities to give access to firms and attract investors who were not in the market previously. They also potentially cause market participants to switch to these more productive and efficient means of intermediation. Philippon argues that against the backdrop of relatively stable high costs of financial intermediation, the new technologies developed by fintech could bring meaningful technological change to the industry if they amount to real disruptive innovations. We consider three main technological advances in this review: platforms, algorithms and distributed ledger technology (DLT).

We group crowdfunding into four categories following a generally accepted classification. The oldest group is lending-based crowdfunding. In this category, startups have sufficient revenues to sustain interest payments and may borrow money on a platform rather than from a bank. Investors make financial decisions and seek a financial return. Lending crowdfunding platforms are often studied together with other P2P lending platforms, a convention we will follow in this review. In doing so, we bundle them with fintech lending more generally in order to study different forms of lending together.

The remaining three categories of crowdfunding deal with other forms of claims held by the crowd. In reward-based crowdfunding, entrepreneurs seek funds to

launch the project and offer backers a reward for their support. The reward is typically either an acknowledgement or a unit of the product that will be commercialized if the project is successful. Backers make non-financial decisions, combining a consumption decision with a donation decision. Initially, many reward-based crowdfunding projects were artistic or contained a strong social component. Nowadays, a large fraction of these projects involve a commercial activity. In equity crowdfunding, startups issue securities such as shares or convertible notes. Investors purchase them either directly and become shareholders, or their investments are pooled in a financial vehicle that collects the funds of the crowd investors and then invests in the startup. Convertibles are increasingly used when retail investors are involved and are structured so that a pre-money valuation of the startup is not needed. Startups rely on equity crowdfunding when they have no revenues to sustain interest payments but need cash for investments. Investors are equity investors, committed for the long-term in highly illiquid shares. Finally, other forms of crowdfunding have emerged, such as royalty-based and real estate crowdfunding. Increasingly, platforms diversify across several types of crowdfunding to facilitate diversification by investors across different asset classes.

The second category of fintech analyzed in our review is fintech lending markets, including lending-based crowdfunding and other P2P lending platforms.

ICOs share some characteristics with crowdfunding, in that investors are also potential consumers of the service and they therefore provide useful feedback to the project team about demand for the project. Many ICO investors have a broader stake in the project than funding, as they join the community of miners which makes the project function. An example of this type of project is Filecoin. Filecoin is a blockchain-technology based project which provides decentralized storage solutions tapping into unused space on hard drives. Miners can generate storage space and earn more Filecoins as a reward. The Filecoin ICO in 2017 raised more than USD 200 million in around 30 min.

ICOs differ from crowdfunding and fintech lending in the exit possibility provided to investors through listing on secondary markets post-ICO. Although analogies are often made between ICOs and Initial public offerings (IPO), there are major differences between them. Contrary to an IPO, in an ICO, there may be a time lag of several months or even years between the ICO and secondary market listing. During this time, ICO investors are locked in or are constrained to resort to over the counter (OTC) trading to exit the project. In the case of Filecoin, fully 3 years elapsed between the ICO in 2017 and secondary market listing in 2020. Future developments in ICOs may include the recourse to platforms for the issuance phase. The French equity-crowdfunding platform Anaxago has recently organized the first ICO on its platform.

The technological advantage of ICOs results from DLT. It came to the fore as the basis for Bitcoin. The technology has two features which make it a disruptive technology for finance. First, it provides the possibility for peer-to-peer interaction at low cost. Second, it is not reliant on a centralizing intermediary either for matching investors and investees, or to store ownership data and record transactions. The commonly used term “blockchain”, which we use here interchangeably with distributed ledger technology, reflects the encryption process which leads to the creation of blocks. Most blockchains rely on “proof of work” for participants (also known as miners) to obtain rewards. Proof of work reflects the effort required to generate new blocks. Effort levels must be high to ensure the security of information on the blockchain. Security is also provided by the distributed nature of information, which is held simultaneously by all participants. It is therefore impossible to falsify information, because this would imply tampering with previous blocks whose details are fully known to all participants. While blockchain is most readily associated with cryptocurrencies, the technology has leant itself readily to project funding in the form of ICOs. Tokens issued during ICOs take the form of digital assets built using DLT. The blockchain can be created by the project itself or be built on an existing technology such as Ethereum. ICOs function according to smart contracts which are

built into the blockchain and are executed automatically when key conditions are met. Contrary to platforms, which share some of the characteristics of traditional financial intermediaries, blockchain-based funding is truly disintermediated.

Conclusion

Although the surge in fintech has definitely impacted the finance industry, there is no compelling evidence so far that it will supplant traditional finance. On balance, it seems that fintech improves access to finance, opening up opportunities for new types of projects and attracting new categories of investors. The new sources of financing have arisen in response to a funding gap in the economy, and taken on forms that are appropriate for small firms, smaller funding amounts, and early-stage innovative startups. At the same time, traditional investors such as banks and venture capitalists have adapted, and the new alternatives and the more traditional forms of finance have drawn closer and increased collaboration. Banks and venture capitalists are pouring funds into fintech on a massive scale, recognizing the value it will create in the future. There is, of course, a long way to go before the fintech market reaches maturity, and many hurdles to overcome to protect investors without snuffing out innovation. It is also likely that fintech will continue to evolve and new innovations will replace or refine existing technologies. This fluidity is a strength but also represents a huge challenge for regulators.

Based on the analysis in this review, we also observe that research in the fintech area is extremely challenging. Challenges are inevitable given that the field is entirely new, and innovations emerge rapidly making it exacting for researchers to keep on top of new developments. We pinpoint three main reasons which make research in this area so demanding. First, for access to finance claims, counterfactuals are very difficult to establish. In common with many topics in corporate finance, endogeneity concerns and the absence of true counterfactuals make it challenging to claim causal relations. There is inevitably a tradeoff between innovative research on emerging topics such as fintech, which contribute to our understanding of new phenomena, and longer and deeper datasets which enable the

implementation of econometric techniques leading to more credible claims for causality. Second, samples used in papers on fintech are often limited in scope as they mostly rely on datasets from platforms. Platforms are heterogeneous players and conditions and mechanisms vary widely. This leads to non-standard data, which makes for a very rich understanding of different platforms but renders results difficult to compare across studies. One might even argue that much research to date compares a multitude of smaller populations, rather than multitude of smaller samples drawn from one population, although some recent studies have started exploring datasets comprising multiple platforms and countries. Finally, existing research on ICOs relies on a relatively short period which is mostly a bubble, and coincided with a wider crypto bubble. It is therefore difficult to generalize results from current papers.

The findings summarized in this review and the papers included in this issue provide us with insights and ideas for future research that may be of interest to researchers in the area of fintech and corporate finance. We believe there are a number of open questions in the field which are worth taking up. First, we need to analyze what is really new about fintech in corporate finance making it different from a technological innovation that simply translates into another funding market access mechanism. As we show in this review, many of the market structure issues, risks and regulatory challenges that arise in fintech have already been studied before in other financial contexts. The field could benefit from linking previous analyses to fintech and pointing to the key aspects that make a difference.

Second, does the fintech meteorite represent such a shock that traditional intermediaries will cease to exist? Will they find a co-existence equilibrium each specializing in the activities in which they have a competitive advantage? Alternatively, will the traditional players consume the relatively fragile fintech players and absorb their technology? These issues worry regulators because the displacement of traditional intermediaries will likely be associated with a high economic cost.

Third, the impact of digital finance on traditional providers and intermediaries raises the question of pathways to funding. The pathways look more complex than current views suggest. For example, VCs participate at different stages – they invest in platforms, and directly in crowdfunding projects. VC may forerun rewards-based crowdfunding. VCs also invest in ICOs (at the pre-sale stage).

P2P business models are affected by the entry of traditional lenders into the market. Greater understanding of the scope of interactions between the different players may help researchers identify their respective benefits and future structures.

References:

1. Butaboyev, M., Urinov, A., Mulaydinov, F., & Tojimatov, I. Digital economy.
2. Горовик, А. А., Мулайдинов, Ф. М., & Лазарева, М. В. (2018). Дистанционное образование как необходимое средство обучения в условиях современной экономики узбекистана. In Цифровой регион: опыт, компетенции, проекты (pp. 122-125).
3. Kokand, F. M., Kokand, R. T., & Kokand, D. M. (2020). Trends in solving problems in the development of an innovative economy. *Journal of Advanced Research in Dynamical and Control Systems*, 12(6), 1205-1209.
4. Мулайдинов, Ф. М. (2021). КИЧИК БИЗНЕС ВА ТАДБИРКОРЛИКДА КРАУДФАНДИНГ ИМКОНИЯТЛАРИ. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 2(Special Issue 4), 23-32.
5. TURSUN, S., TUYCHIEVICH, B. M., & MUROTOVICH, M. F. (2020). Effects of the Global Crisis on the Economy of Uzbekistan During the Coronavirus Pandemia and Measures to Ease IT. *JournalNX*, 6(05), 277-280.
6. Mulaydinov, F. M. (2021). CROWDFUND OPPORTUNITIES IN SMALL BUSINESS AND ENTREPRENEURSHIP. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 2, 23-32.
7. Mulaydinov, F., & Nishonqulov, S. (2021). The role of information technologies in the development of the digital economy. The role of information technologies in the development of the digital economy.

8. Farkhod, M., Azadkhon, K., Gulkhon, M., & Oybek, A. (2020). Advantages of the transition to a digital economy in the innovative development of Uzbekistan. *Journal of Advanced Research in Dynamical and Control Systems*, 12(6), 1226-1232.
9. Mulaydinov, F., & Nishonqulov, S. (2021). Raqamli iqtisodiyotni rivojlantirishda axborot texnologiyalarining orni-The role of information technologies in the development of the digital economy.
10. Mulaydinov, F. M. (2019). Econometric Modelling of the Innovation Process in Uzbekistan. *Форум молодых ученых*, (3), 35-43.
11. Farkhod, M. (2020). Econometric Modelling of the Innovation Process in Uzbekistan. *International Journal of Psychosocial Rehabilitation*, 24(02).
12. Mulaydinov, F. (2021). Digital Economy Is A Guarantee Of Government And Society Development. *Ilkogretim Online*, 20(3), 1474-1479.
13. Farhodjon ogli, N. S., & Odil ogli, R. B. (2021). Raqamli iqtisodiyot almashinuvining resurslar sarfiga sakkizta tasiri. *Бошқарув ва Этика Қоидалари онлайн илмий журнали*, 1(1), 53-56.